

Interaction of Sulphuryl Chloride with Substances Containing the Reactive Methylene (CH_2) Group.

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The reactivity of the hydrogens of a methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) group in compounds containing $-\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$ and $-\text{CN}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$ has been taken advantage of in numerous condensations. Some light has been thrown on the factors which govern the reactivity of the methylene group, in substituted malonamides, with the help of sulphur monochloride (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 379; 1921, 119, 1231; Naik and Avasare, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 2592; Naik and Patel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 27). It was decided to carry this subject further by studying the interaction of substituted malonamides and sulphuryl chloride. The results show that sulphuryl chloride can react as a chlorinating agent on the methylene group, and, also, in certain cases, on aromatic nuclei.¹

In view of chlorination having been already effected with the help of sulphuryl chloride, it was expected that in the substituted malonamides containing aromatic nuclei, the chlorine might attack both the methylene group and the aromatic nucleus, and that only when the reactivity of both the hydrogens of the methylene group $-\text{CH}_2-$, was sufficiently modified by the proximity of other groups, that sulphuryl chloride would attack the nucleus. This has been found to happen in certain cases.

Chlorination with sulphuryl chloride seems to have been studied by various workers (*Zeit. Chem. von Beilstein u. Hubner*, 1866, 2, 705; Dubois, *Bull. Acad. roy. Belg.*, 1876, 42, 126; Töhl and Elurhardt, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 2940; Peratoner, *Gazzetta*, 1894, 24, 1, 286; Wöhl, D.R.-PP. 139552, 1467/1902, 160102/1902, 162394/1903; Silberrad, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 2029; *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1015; Durrans, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 44; Elber and Klemm, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 217; Macbeth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1116; *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 1122; Durrans, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1424; Bulow and King, *Annalen*, 1924, 439, 311; Fuchs and Katscher, *Ber.*, 1924, 57[B], 1256; Silberrad and Parke, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1724; Silberrad, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2677.)

The main results of the interaction of sulphuryl chloride with various mono- and di-substituted amides of malonic and methylmalonic acids can be summarised as under:—

Conversion of the group $-\text{CH}_2-$ *into* CCl_2 ,

(a) without chlorination of the nucleus: malondiphenylamide, malondibenzylamide, malon-di-*o*-tolylamide, malon-di-*p*-tolylamide; malon-dipropylamide and malon-mono-*p*-tolylamide undergo this change;

(b) with chlorination of the nucleus; malon-di-*m*-tolylamide, malon-mono-phenylamide and malon-di- β -naphthylamide undergo this change.

II. *Conversion of the group* $-\text{CH}_2-$ *into* $-\text{CHCl}-$

(a) without chlorination of the nucleus: malon-dimethylphenylamide undergoes this change;

(b) with chlorination of the nucleus: malon-di- σ -naphthylamide undergoes this change.

III. *Conversion of the group* $-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-$ *into* $\text{CCl}(\text{CH}_2\text{Cl})$: methylmalondiphenylamide, methylmalon-di-*o*-tolylamide and methylmalon-di-*p*-tolylamide undergo this change.

Type I. (a). Malondiphenylamide reacts with sulphuryl chloride as under:—

(I)

That the substance produced from malon diphenylamide has the constitution follows from the facts enumerated below:—

(1) The two hydrogen atoms that are replaced by chlorine, are not supplied by the phenyl group because (a) a similar dichloro-derivative is obtained from malondipropylamide; (b) the chlorine atoms can be replaced again by hydrogen with production of the original amide by the action of sodium hydrosulphide (Brand, *Ber.*, 1906, 42, 3464), and by potassium iodide and hydrochloric acid (Meyer, *Annalen*, 1911, 380, 212).

(2) The hydrogen atoms that are replaced by chlorine are not attached to the nitrogen atoms, because malon-dimethylanilide, where there is no hydrogen attached to the nitrogen, yields a monochloro-derivative.

Type I (b). In the case of malon-*m*-tolylamide, the reaction was more vigorous (giving rise to a tetrachloro-derivative) than with the corresponding *o*- and *p*-compounds.

Of the four chlorine atoms present in this compound, two are attached to the methylene carbon as is evident by the reduction with potassium iodide and concentrated hydrochloric acid. The other two halogen atoms which are present in the compound, even after reduction, may be present either in the ortho- or para-position to the amino-group in the aromatic nucleus.

On studying the behaviour of malon-di- β -naphthylamide with sulphuryl chloride, there was a copious evolution of hydrogen chloride and sulphur dioxide. The tetrachloro-compound thus formed lost, on reduction by the above method, two atoms of chlorine, which were attached to the methylene carbon. Malon-monophenylamide exhibits a similar reactivity, and the reaction proceeds as under:—

Type II (a). The interaction of malon-dimethylphenylamide with sulphuryl chloride results in the production of a monochloro compound.

In spite of the two hydrogen atoms of the methylene group being available only one is attacked. This course of the reaction is not an abnormal one, as is evident from the work of Naik (*loc. cit.*) and West (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2196).

Type II (b). When α -naphthylamide was made to react with sulphuryl chloride in the ratio of 1: 3, a trichloro-compound was obtained.

That in this trichloro-compound, only one chlorine is attached to the methylene carbon, and the other two are substituted in the aromatic nuclei, is shown by the study of its reduction with potassium iodide and hydrochloric acid.

It is curious that malon-di- α -naphthylamide gives a trichloro-derivative, whereas the corresponding β -compound gives a tetrachloro-derivative under similar conditions. That the difference between the behaviour of α -naphthyl compounds and β -naphthyl

compounds is general was noticed by other workers (Whiteley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 24), and was attributed to various reasons (Weinberg, *Ber.*, 1924, 54[B], 2168).

Type III. Further, it was desirable to see if the same type and reactivity persisted amongst the corresponding derivatives of methylmalonic acid. Here one of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group is replaced by the methyl group, so that a monochloro derivative might be expected on interaction with sulphuryl chloride. Yet, in the three cases that were studied, dichloro-derivatives were formed. On reduction of these by the usual method it was found that both the chlorine atoms were replaced by hydrogen. Hence the second chlorine atom must have entered the methyl radicle. If the second chlorine atom had entered the benzene nucleus, it could not have been reduced by the above method, nor could it have come in place of the hydrogen of the imino ($-\text{NHR}-$) group, as was pointed out previously. Thus:

(where R represents either a phenyl or a tolyl group).

The above dichloro-compounds showed no trace of any free hydrogen chloride contained in them; for, when they were shaken with water, the filtrate gave no reaction with silver nitrate. Examples of chlorination similar to this are known (*cf.* Willgerodt and Durr, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 539). The mechanism of this interesting course of chlorination is discussed later on.

Coming to the question of reactivity of the hydrogens of the methylene group in grouping such as $-\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$, $-\text{CN}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$ etc., it is interesting to note that the experiments described here afford clear evidence that the interaction of sulphuryl chloride with compounds containing the methylene radicle depends on the total negativity of the groups attached to the two remaining valencies of the carbon atom (*loc. cit.*) If these valencies carry neutral groups such as $\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}_2$, as in malonamide no interaction occurs with sulphuryl chloride. If, however, the neutral character of either or both of the carboxylamide groups is disturbed by the entrance of phenyl, tolyl, etc., interaction with sulphuryl chloride readily occurs.

The reactivity of sulphuryl chloride with malonic ester, acetoacetic ester, cyanacetic ester, etc., has been studied by Macbeth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1120; 1923, 123, 1125), who obtained

chloro-compounds. In all such cases, the reactivity of the sulphuryl chloride with esters was found to be great, certainly greater than the reactivity of the corresponding amido and substituted amido derivatives.

Although no definite measurements have as yet been made, it is evident that the speed of the reaction depends on the total negativity of the attached groups. For example, sulphuryl chloride reacts more vigorously with compound (iii, R=Ph) than with (ii, R=Tol) whilst the reaction with the ester itself is the most vigorous, even taking place at the ordinary temperature. So in a series like

- (i) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CONH}_2)_2$,
- (ii) $\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR}$ (R=Ph, Tol etc.)
- (iii) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CONHR})_2$
- (iv) $\text{CH}_2(\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5)_2$,

the reactivity which is absent in (i) is found in (ii) and goes on increasing through the series (Naik, *loc. cit.*).

The reactivity of the CH_2 group may be referred to (a) polarity (Macbeth and his collaborators, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 892, 904, 1109, 1116, 2169, 2527, 2601; 1923, 123, 124, 1122; 1925, 127, 892, 1118), (b) to keto-enol transformation (Thorpe and his collaborators, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 2188; 1921, 119, 1203; 1922, 121, 1896), or (c) to the combined influences of polarity effects, steric influence and structural characteristics such as would give rise to keto-enol transformations (West, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 710).

The reactivity of the compounds investigated herein can be explained on the basis of keto-enol transformation. In the cases where both the hydrogens of the methylene group are replaced by chlorine atoms, the substance, according to Norris and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1203), assumes an enolic form. Thus in the case of formation of compound I, the course followed can be represented thus:

By a similar series of changes the final product is the dichloro-compound, $\text{CCl}_2(\text{CONHPh})_2$.

In the case of malon-dimethylphenylamide, only one hydrogen is reactive. It appears that after one of the two hydrogen atoms has reacted, the other becomes sluggish, only a monochloro-compound being obtained. West (*loc. cit.*) has shown that further chlorination of this amide is not possible on passing more chlorine. This sluggishness of the second hydrogen atom can be explained as being due to the stability of the keto-form as in the case of acetyl acetone (Norris and Thorpe, *loc. cit.*), which gives a monobromo-compound, $(\text{CH}_3\cdot\text{CO})_2\text{CHBr}$. Further bromination does not take place.

In some cases, however, enolisation involves a hydrogen atom of a terminal methyl group. For example, in the case of methylmalondiphenyl amide, after the group $-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)\text{Cl}$ has been formed, enolisation involves a hydrogen atom of the methyl group:

Such a change due to the enolisation of a terminal methyl group was noticed by Hantzsch (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 356, 3168).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dichloromalondiphenylamide.

Malondiphenylamide (2 g.) was made to react with sulphuryl chloride (2.25 g.) in presence of dry benzene (50 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed for four hours over a water-bath. Dense fumes of sulphur dioxide and hydrogen chloride were evolved. When the reaction was over, the solution was filtered hot and the filtrate, on cooling, deposited a white crystalline mass. This was filtered, washed repeatedly with dry petroleum to free it from excess of sulphuryl chloride, and crystallised from hot benzene, m.p. 127°.

It is fairly soluble in acetone, chloroform, ethyl acetate and nitrobenzene, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, toluene, acetic acid and carbon tetrachloride, and insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 21.8. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 21.96 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound with Hydriodic Acid.—The dichloro-compound (0.1498 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.). To the solution, potassium iodide (1.85 g.) dissolved in water (20 c.c.) was added, and then concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hours at about 60°. A control experiment was set up at the same time with the same amount of absolute alcohol, potassium iodide and concentrated hydrochloric acid, for the same period; and from the observations in the control experiment, a correction was introduced in the observations of the actual reduction experiment. The substance liberated iodine equivalent to 19.8 c.c. of 0.0971N sodium thiosulphate solution. (Found: Cl (equivalent of the iodine liberated), 22.16. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 21.96 per cent.).

Reduction of Dichloromalondiphenylamide with alkaline Hydro-sulphide.—The chloride (2 g.) was added to absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) and refluxed for about half an hour. An aqueous solution of sodium hydrosulphide, prepared by saturating sodium hydroxide (0.3 g.) dissolved in a small quantity of water with hydrogen sulphide, was gradually added to it. After a time the whole went into solution with a brown colour. On cooling a slight crystalline precipitate appeared. The solution was diluted with water (500 c.c.) and filtered. The substance was washed free from alkali by hot water. The product was then crystallised from acetic acid, and was found to be pure malondiphenylamide, m.p. 224-225°.

Dichloromalon-dibenzylamide.

This substance was prepared from malon-dibenzylamide (2 g.), and sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) in presence of dry benzene (50 c.c.) as before. It was deposited as a white mass sparingly soluble in benzene, from which it was crystallised in white shining plates, m.p. 170-171°.

It is fairly soluble in chloroform, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, acetone, toluene, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride, ethyl acetate, carbon bisulphide, ether and nitrobenzene, but insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 19.82. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 20.20 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-di-o-tolylamide.

This substance was prepared from malon-di-o-tolylamide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) in the usual way. The white solid is sparingly soluble in alcohol, from which it was crystallised in white needles, m.p. 140-141°.

It is fairly soluble in acetone, chloroform, ethyl acetate, carbon bisulphide and nitrobenzene, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, toluene, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride and ether, but insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 20·15. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 20·20 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-di-p-tolylamide.

The above compound was obtained as a white amorphous powder when malon-di-p-tolylamide (2 g.) was treated with sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) in the usual way. It was crystallised from alcohol in shining white needles, m.p. 145-146°.

It is fairly soluble in benzene, acetone, chloroform, toluene, acetic acid, ethyl acetate, carbon bisulphide, ether and nitrobenzene, sparingly so in alcohol and carbon tetrachloride, but insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 20·01. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 20·20 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-dipropylamide.

It was prepared by the action of sulphuryl chloride (3 g.) on malon-dipropylamide (2 g.) in the usual way. The solid product was crystallised from benzene in shining cubes, m.p. 108-109°.

It is fairly soluble in acetone, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, chloroform, toluene, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride, ethyl acetate carbon bisulphide, ether and nitrobenzene, but insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 27·83. $C_9H_{15}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 27·82 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-mono-p-tolylamide.

It was prepared from malon-mono-p-tolylamide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) in the usual way. A white solid was obtained, which on crystallisation from benzene melted at 145-146°.

It is fairly soluble in acetone, ethyl acetate and ether, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, chloroform, toluene, acetic acid, carbon bisulphide and nitrobenzene, but almost insoluble in petroleum and carbon tetrachloride. (Found: Cl, 27·1. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 27·17 per cent.).

Preparation of Malon-di-m-tolylamide.

Malonic ester and pure *m*-toluidine were taken in molecular proportions in a flask provided with a cork, through which a wide tube passed. This tube was bent at the top and was fitted into a condenser. The length of the tube from the cork upwards to the bend at the top measured 15 cm. The flask was put in a paraffin-bath and maintained at 130-140° for four hours, when alcohol distilled off drop by drop. The temperature at the end was raised to 150°. The rate of the distillation was so regulated that for every drop of alcohol distilled, fifteen drops of the liquid returned to the flask. This increased the yield of the diamide. The liquid was then transferred to a mortar, where it solidified on cooling. The solid was extracted with alcohol and finally washed with a little ether. When crystallised from acetic acid, it was obtained in brilliant needles, m.p. 152°.

It is fairly soluble in chloroform, ethyl acetate and nitrobenzene, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, acetone, toluene, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide and ether, but almost insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: N, 9·8. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2N_2$, requires N, 9·9 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-di-m-tolylamide dichloride.

On treating malon-di-*m*-tolylamide (2 g.) with sulphuryl chloride (4 g.) in the usual way a white mass was deposited on standing. The resulting product was crystallised from benzene in cubic crystals, m.p. 164°.

It is fairly soluble in acetone, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, chloroform, toluene, acetic acid, ethyl acetate, ether and nitrobenzene, but almost insoluble in carbon tetrachloride and light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 33·51. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl_2$, requires Cl, 33·78 per cent.)

Dichloromalon-monochlorphenylamide.

This compound was prepared from malon-mono-phenylamide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (3 g.) in the same way as the preceding chloride. After the reaction was over, the product crystallised immediately on cooling. On recrystallising from benzene, it yielded shining pearly plates, m.p. 136°.

It is fairly soluble in acetone, ethyl acetate and ether, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, chloroform, toluene, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide and nitrobenzene, but almost insoluble in light petroleum. (Found : Cl, 57.67. $C_{11}H_9O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 57.80 per cent.)

Dichloromalon-di-β-naphthylamide dichloride.

The above compound was obtained as a white amorphous powder, when malon-di-β-naphthylamide and sulphuryl chloride were treated in the usual way. It was crystallised from benzene, in which it is difficultly soluble, in shining crystals, m.p. 183°.

It is sparingly soluble in benzene, alcohol, chloroform, toluene, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride, ethyl acetate and nitrobenzene, but almost insoluble in light petroleum, acetone, carbon bisulphide and ether. (Found : Cl, 29.25. $C_{22}H_{14}O_4N_4Cl_4$ requires Cl, 28.84 per cent.)

Monochloromalon-dimethylphenylamide.

Malondimethyl-phenylamide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) were made to react in the usual way described. The amorphous white product, when crystallised from absolute alcohol, yielded colourless prisms, m.p. 187°.

It is fairly soluble in chloroform, sparingly so in acetic acid, ethyl alcohol, acetone, toluene, ethyl acetate, nitrobenzene, and carbon bisulphide, but nearly insoluble in light petroleum, carbon tetrachloride and ether. (Found : Cl, 11.44. $C_{17}H_{17}O_2N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.2 per cent.)

This chloro-compound was prepared by West (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2196) by direct chlorination of the amide.

Chloromalon-di-α-naphthylamide dichloride.

This compound was prepared from malon-di-α-naphthylamide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (2.5 g.) in the usual way. The mass obtained, when crystallised from benzene, gave pure shining cubic crystals, m.p. 182°.

It is fairly soluble in chloroform and nitrobenzene, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, acetone, toluene, acetic acid and ethyl acetate, but nearly insoluble in light petroleum, carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide and ether. (Found : Cl, 23.41. $C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 23.23 per cent.)

Chloromethyl-chloromalon-diphenylamide.

The above substance was prepared from methylmalondiphenylamide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) in the usual way. The solid was precipitated from a large quantity of petroleum. On crystallisation from a small amount of benzene, it gave shining pearly plates, m.p. 128°.

It is fairly soluble in acetone, ethyl acetate, chloroform, ether and nitrobenzene, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, toluene, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride and carbon bisulphide, but almost insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 21.18. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl_2$, requires Cl, 21.05 per cent.)

Chloromethyl-chloromalon-di-o-tolylamide.

This compound was obtained from methylmalon-di-o-tolylamide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) as above. The white solid, on crystallisation from a benzene-petrol mixture, gave a feathery mass, m.p. 130°.

It is fairly soluble in acetone, ethyl acetate and nitrobenzene, sparingly so in benzene, alcohol, chloroform, toluene, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide and ether, but insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 19.88. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_2Cl_2$, requires Cl, 19.43 per cent.)

Chloromethyl-chloromalon-di-p-tolylamide.

The above compound was obtained as shining white needles, when methylmalon-di-p-tolylamide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) were made to react in the usual way. It was recrystallised from benzene, in which it is sparingly soluble: m.p. 138°.

The solubility of the chloride was of the same order as the preceding chloride. (Found: Cl, 19.81. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_2Cl_2$, requires Cl, 19.43 per cent.)

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